

Abstract: In this article, information about the history and understanding of all the possibilities of the Internet is given, and the majority of people in the world are using the Internet, which means that people and society do not stand still, they are always changing, and the time we live in is called the era of globalization. information is given that it has become a common situation.

Key words: internet browsers, internet, world, web, internet network, internet speed, information technologies.

In order to understand all the possibilities on the Internet, you need a little title on the history of its emergence. The concept of "Internet" includes computers connected to a network, a global flow of information exchange, and computing resources.

The Internet took off in 1973. At this time, the "scientific" network was joined by an organization in Norway and England using a transatlantic cable for a telephone line. This event marks the birth of the Internet. , flying for almost forty years. Since then, computer networks have moved to amazing proportions. available now for most applicants.

The World Wide Web is a global World Wide Web. Many people think that behind this word is just a beautiful metaphor, but I think it is not. World (World) Wide (Vaidya) Web (Web) - In fact, these symbols consisting of three "w" are analyzed. In some sense, it creates a site. The program is called Internet browsers and is used to view the page in question. Hearing online today, or saying the word "Internet", many people, perhaps, do not think about the technical side of the idea, rather than what the web has presented to modern people. By analyzing the reasons why people spend a lot of time online, you can analyze the most important opportunities for ordinary Internet users: Communication. Social networks, forums, text and video blogs, dating sites, Skype.

The main purpose of all the above is to remove a barrier in the form of distance for free communication.

Entertainment. Games, music, movies, videos, books, and more can be downloaded.

Self-education. Books, tutorials, educational videos, courses and much more, very useful experience for those who want to conquer a certain area.

Creativity and handmade. It is not difficult to find news about cooking or knitting on the open spaces of the network.

Today, most of the world's population uses the Internet. Man and society do not stay in one place, they are always changing, the current time we live in is called the era of globalization. The development of means of data transmission served to create a single information system that includes all countries. It is thanks to the Internet that local information networks merge into a single global network.

It is important to note that the leadership of our republic pays great attention to the development of this sector. In particular, a meeting was held in the presence of the President of Uzbekistan on January 9, 2018, regarding the state of development of information and communication systems and technologies in the republic, and the further acceleration of reforms in this field. The leaders of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development gave a report at this meeting. Full and timely fulfillment of the tasks set at the meeting, including a sharp increase in Internet speed and quality improvement, increasing the types of mobile services, strengthening relations with leading international telecommunications companies, further developing the "Electronic Government" system, and ensuring information security. relevant assignments were given.

Due to the lack of a competitive environment for the provision of Internet connection services in Uzbekistan and the fact that the northern, that is, Kazakhstan depends on the Russian Internet channel, the Internet connection is much slower and more expensive than in the CIS countries. Uzbekistan plans to solve this problem by opening new external channels. It is planned to increase the speed and stability of Internet connection by opening new external channels through the countries of Turkmenistan, Iran, Kyrgyzstan and China. By the end of this year, agreements on renting and buying channels will be signed with the national operators of these countries.

At the same time, no one is thinking about giving up the channel in the northern direction, but new additional channels will appear along with it, which will cover the needs of the population. The implementation of these works will ensure the high speed of the Internet in our country and make it much cheaper.

Looking at the Internet as a "scourge" that propagates foreign ideas and leads to the world of crime, parents should first remember to distinguish between the useful and harmful aspects of it, without banning our children from accessing the Internet. it is necessary and important for us to learn. After that, we need to explain to our children that this or that resource or social network can harm them morally or materially, while others can help them improve their spirituality, knowledge and skills. In addition, there are sites on the Internet that are overflowing with useful resources on how to start a

business and so on. In short, the Internet is a source of endless opportunities to earn money. If we can explain all these things to our children, if we instill in them from a young age that they can earn income on their own by using the appropriate resources of the Internet, then our children will not waste their time, and will not waste their time on their parents. decreasing his age, he wants to add his own share to the family budget.

For information, we remind you that by creating a comfortable and safe environment for the growing young generation on the Internet, by organizing them to use a single point of educational and educational resources, which have a negative impact on their health and development. In order to protect against information and cyber-attacks, in 2017, "Uzbektelecom" AK introduced special tariff plans, "safe Internet" series and additional services.

Now the Internet users of the company connect to the services of the "ZiyoNET" tariff plan and give their children the opportunity to use the Unified information resources, which currently includes about 3 thousand sites. This list includes scientific-educational, spiritual-educational and other national and international Internet pages that serve the child's mature and healthy growth. This ensures that children are protected from the dangers of the Internet, access to various malicious and ideologically inappropriate sites. Also, parents can make a proposal to add to the list their favorite sites that are interesting for children.

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